

A STUDY ON THE BACTERIOLOGICAL PROFILE AND ANTIMICROBIAL SUSCEPTIBILITY PATTERN OF SURGICAL INFECTIONS IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL, NAVI MUMBAI.

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ABSTRACT-

Surgical infections as those that follow a surgical procedure, and that can certainly be true for an incisional surgical site infection (SSI) or a postoperative intraabdominal abscess. A Study on the Bacteriological Profile and Antimicrobial Susceptibility Pattern of Surgical Infections. Aerobic organisms isolated from surgical infections and their antibiotic susceptibility pattern also the correlation of various surgical sites with isolated organisms was studied. A total 1250 pus samples from various surgical infection were received and processed aerobically according to standard microbiological procedure. AST was done by Kirby- Bauer's disc diffusion method. Depending upon the type of organisms isolated antibiotic disc were selected and measure zone size according to CLSI guidelines. Out of 1250, the bacterial growth was seen in 160 samples (12.8%), Other surgical infections (92.5%), Post surgical infections/SSI (7.5%). Gram negative bacteria (54%) were more as compared to Gram positive bacteria (46%) in causing Surgical Infections. Our study emphasizes the need of quality surgical care which may take into consideration all the three important factors, i.e. host, environmental, and microorganism characteristics before doing any surgery. Also suggests, the judicious use of antibiotics and establishment of antibiotic policy in the hospital.

Keywords- Surgical Infections, Antimicrobial Susceptibility Pattern, Kirby- Bauer's disc diffusion.

INTRODUCTION

Surgical infections are those that follow a surgical procedure, and that can certainly be true for an incisional surgical site infection (SSI) or a postoperative intraabdominal abscess.[1]

Invasive procedures are linked to surgical infections, which include postoperative infections, such as infections at suture sites, and surgically-related disorders, such as appendicitis and diabetic foot ulcers. The CDC has developed classification categories for four groups of wound states:

1. Class 1 wounds are considered to be clean.
2. Class 2 wounds are considered to be clean-contaminated.
3. Class 3 wounds are considered to be contaminated.
4. Class 4 wounds are considered to be dirty-infected.

Both endogenous and external sources of infection are possible in surgical patients. Endogenous infections are typically brought on by organisms that reside in patients but are not harmful to them, for example, resident flora like *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Diphtheroid*, *Micrococci*, Gram negative bacilli, and transient flora like *Pseudomonas spp.*, other gram-negative organisms, *Clostridium* spores, etc. Exogenous sources—those outside the patient's body—of exogenous illnesses commonly include other patients or other infectious disease carriers. For instance, *Salmonella*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Streptococcus pyogenes*. [2]

In 2019–20, 1,88,82,734 procedures were carried out at India's public healthcare facilities, according to HIMS data. 48,51,788 major surgeries and 1,40,30,946 minor ones were performed. During the reference period, 23,286 patients nationwide who had surgeries experienced surgical site infections. [3]

The CDC's advice for SSI prevention emphasises the importance of aseptic procedure, attention to surgical technique, antibiotic prophylaxis, and appropriate patient preparation. In order to identify cases of increasing antibiotic resistance and, consequently, to encourage the hospital to use more and reserve antibiotics sparingly, our study also examined the trend of antibiotic resistance. Additionally, our study helped formulate an antibiogram for Surgical Infection, which aided in the implementation of antibiotic policy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was carried from January 2022 to December 2022 in MGM Hospital Kamothe, Navi Mumbai. It was a descriptive and prospective study.

Sample collection - Pus samples were obtained from open and sutured wounds of elective surgery patients in the hospital's surgical, post-operative, trauma, and orthopaedic departments. Collection was performed under strict aseptic conditions using the Levine technique [4] and fine needle syringes (FNS), aiming to achieve the required sample size of 160, as determined by a standard sample size calculation formula.

Transportation of sample- The collected specimens were transported using Amies transfer medium.

Processing of sample - All samples were inoculated onto Blood agar, MacConkey agar, and Mannitol Salt Agar (MSA) using the streak culture method. A primary smear was prepared

and stained using the Gram staining technique. Bacterial identification was carried out using conventional methods.

Susceptibility testing - All the bacterial isolates were subjected to Antibiotic Susceptibility test by Kirby Bauer's disk diffusion method (Mackie & McCartney 1996) Antibiotics used were Levofloxacin (5mcg), Co-trimoxazole (25mcg), Ofloxacin (mcg), Cefoperazone (75mcg), Tetracycline (30mcg), Ticarcillin-Clavulanate (75/10 mcg), Meropenem (10mcg), Cefuroxime (30mcg), Amoxicillin- Clavulanate (20/10mcg), Gentamicin (10mcg), Polymyxin-B (300 units), Ceftazidime (30mcg), Aztreonam (30mcg), Cefepime (30mcg), Imipenem (10 mcg), Ciprofloxacin (5 mcg), Piperacillin-Tazobactam (100/10 mcg), Cefoperazone + Sulbactam (75/30 mcg), Nalidixic Acid (30 mcg), Amikacin (30 mcg), Cefofaxim (30mcg), Penicillin (10mcg), Clindamycin (2mcg), Roxithromycin (30 mcg), Erythromycin (15mcg), Clarithromycin (15mcg), Linezolid (30mcg), Vancomycin (30mcg), Azithromycin (15 mcg). and interpretation as per recent CLSI guidelines. [5,6]

The rate of SSI in our study was calculated using following formula.[7]

- Surgical Site Infection rate = $\frac{\text{Number of Surgical Site Infection} \times 100}{\text{Number of Surgeries Done}}$

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this study, a total of 1,250 samples were collected from different surgical sites. Among these, 160 samples (12.8%) exhibited bacterial growth. In comparison, the study by AtsedewoyinFiresbhat et al. (2021) reported that out of 384 processed samples, 102 (26.6%) were culture-positive. [5]

Table 1 presents the distribution of various surgical infections, including surgical site infections (SSI). In our study, the SSI rate was calculated to be 0.29% using a standard formula. This finding is consistent with the results of Mabit et al. (2012), who reported SSI rates ranging from 0.66% to 1.86% [8]. Most SSI cases in our study were associated with type 3 (contaminated) wounds. Furthermore, necrotic tissue was identified as the most frequent site of surgical infections in this study.

Table 1: Segregation of Other Surgical Infections And SSI

Other surgical infections (148 i.e. 92.5%)			Post surgical infections/SSI (12 i.e. 7.5%)		
Types of surgical infections	Total number	Percentage	Types of wounds	Total number	Percentage
Necrotising Tissue	63	39.3%	Type 2 Wound	2	16.6%
Infection In Cavity	32	20%	Type 3wound	7	58.33%
Organ /Tissue Infection	53	33.12%	Type 4 Wound	3	25%

Note: The above table describes the segregation of other surgical infections and surgical site infection.

Table 2 and Graph 1 display the demographic details of the study population. Surgical infections were more prevalent in males (72%) than in females (28%), resulting in a male-to-

female ratio of 2.5:1. This disparity could be due to differences in occupational exposure between genders. In terms of age distribution, individuals over 55 years were the most affected, representing 49 cases (30.60%), while the 18–25-year age group had the fewest cases, with 20 (12.50%). Likewise, a study by Sulaiman Lakoh et al. reported a greater incidence of infections in males, accounting for 192 cases (56.8%). Similarly, research conducted by Mengistu Abayneh et al. (2022) found that over half of the participants 145 individuals (55.3%) belonged to the 19–35-year age group. [9,10]

Table 2: Demographic characteristics of study

Characteristics		N (%)
Gender	Male	116(72%)
	Female	44(28%)
Age category	<25	20 (12.4%)
	26-35	22 (13.75%)
	36-45	33 (20.6%)
	46-55	36 (22.5%)
	>55	49 (30.6%)

Note: Above table shows the demographic characteristics of patients.

Graph 1: Demographic characteristics of study

Table 3 and Graph 2 show the distribution of surgical infection cases according to wound type. Deep surgical infections were the most common, observed in 73 patients (46%), followed closely by superficial infections in 70 cases (44%). Space infections were the least frequent, reported in only 17 patients (10%).

A comparable study by Sulaiman Lakoh et al. (2022) found that among 39 infection cases, 12 (31%) were superficial, while 27 (69%) were categorized as deep (profound) infections. [10]

Table 3. Distribution of Surgical Infection Patients based on their Types of wounds

Types	N (%)
Superficial	70 (44%)
Deep	73 (46%)
Space	17 (10%)

Note: Above table shows the distribution of surgical infections based on types of wounds.

Graph 2. Distribution of Surgical Infection Patients based on their Types of wounds

Table 4 summarizes the total number of organisms isolated from surgical infections. Gram-negative bacteria were more commonly identified, accounting for 54% of the isolates, compared to 46% Gram-positive isolates. Among the Gram-negative organisms, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was the most frequently isolated (18.6%), followed by *E. coli* (16.2%), *Klebsiella spp.* (16.2%), and *Enterobacter spp.* (16.2%). *Acinetobacter spp.* (10.4%) and *Proteus spp.* (8.1%) were the least frequently isolated among Gram-negative bacteria. For Gram-positive isolates, *Staphylococcus aureus* was the most prevalent (59.21%), followed by coagulase-negative staphylococci (CONS) at 22.97%. The least commonly isolated Gram-positive organisms were *Streptococcus pyogenes* and *Enterococcus spp.*, each accounting for 8.1%.

In a related study by Mengistu Abayneh et al., a total of 41 bacterial isolates were identified, with 30 (73.2%) being Gram-negative and 11 (26.8%) Gram-positive. Additionally, 8 isolates (24.2%) exhibited mixed bacterial growth. [9]

Table 4: Total Number of Organisms Isolated

Isolates	Organisms	N (%)
Gram Positive (46%)	<i>S. aureus</i>	45 (59.21%)
	CONS	17 (22.97%)
	<i>Enterococcus</i>	6 (8.1%)
	<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	6 (8.1%)
Gram Negative (54%)	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	16 (18.6%)
	<i>Klebsiella spp</i>	14 (16.2%)
	<i>Enterobacter spp</i>	14 (16.2%)
	<i>E. coli</i>	14 (16.2%)
	<i>Citrobacter</i>	12 (13.9%)
	<i>Acinetobacter spp</i>	9 (10.4%)
	<i>Proteus</i>	7 (8.1%)

Note: Above table shows the total number of various GPC and GNB.

In this study, *Staphylococcus aureus* demonstrated the highest resistance to Penicillin (95.6%) and Amoxiclav (88.9%). Out of 45 *S. aureus* isolates, 17 (37.8%) were identified as methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) based on ceftazidime resistance. *Enterococcus* spp. showed the greatest resistance to Cefazolin, Azithromycin, and Cefuroxime, each at 83.4%. Among coagulase-negative staphylococci (CoNS), Azithromycin (94.2%) and Roxithromycin (100%) were the most resisted antibiotics. Additionally, 11.7% (2 of 17) of the CoNS isolates were methicillin-resistant (MR-CoNS). *Streptococcus pyogenes* exhibited the highest resistance to Roxithromycin at 66.7%. Despite the resistance trends, several antibiotics demonstrated susceptibility against Gram-positive organisms. These included Tetracycline (77.5%), Cefazolin (56%), Clindamycin (54%), Co-trimoxazole (53%), Gentamicin (77.4%), Ceftazidime (71%), Vancomycin (75%), Netilmicin (83.3%), and Linezolid (72.2%).

In a similar study conducted by DagninetAlelign et al., Gram-positive bacterial isolates showed resistance to Penicillin (75%), Erythromycin (53.1%), Cotrimoxazole (50%), Gentamicin (43.8%), and Clindamycin (43.8%). The most frequently isolated organism, *S. aureus*, demonstrated resistance to Penicillin (78.9%), Cotrimoxazole (63.2%), and Erythromycin (57.9%). MRSA accounted for 57.9% (11 out of 19) of the *S. aureus* isolates, while 40% (4 out of 10) of CoNS isolates were identified as MR-CoNS. Similarly, 33.3% of isolated *Enterococcus faecium* strains were vancomycin-resistant (VRE), whereas 66.7% were susceptible to both chloramphenicol and vancomycin.[11]

In this study, *Citrobacter* spp. showed the highest resistance to Amoxiclav (91.7%) and Cefuroxime (83.4%). *Proteus* spp. exhibited high resistance to Tetracycline (71.5%), Amoxiclav (71.5%), Cefuroxime (71.5%), and Cefazolin (71.5%). *Acinetobacter* spp. demonstrated complete resistance (100%) to Cefoperazone, Amoxiclav, Cefuroxime, and Cefazolin. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was most resistant to Cefuroxime (100%), followed by Amoxiclav (93.75%) and Cefazolin (93.75%). *Klebsiella* spp. showed the highest resistance to Amoxiclav (100%), with Cefuroxime and Cefazolin both at 92.9%. Similarly, *Enterobacter* spp. exhibited high resistance to Amoxiclav (92.8%), Cefuroxime (92.8%), and Cefazolin (92.9%).

Despite the overall resistance patterns, some antibiotics remained effective against Gram-negative organisms. These included Tobramycin (51.4%), Gentamicin (49.4%), Amikacin (55.5%), Ofloxacin (56%), Tetracycline (47.2%), Polymyxin-B (79.8%), Imipenem (43%), and Levofloxacin (77.2%).

In a comparable study by DagninetAlelign et al., the majority of Gram-negative bacterial isolates (over 43.2%) exhibited resistance to Ampicillin, Cefepime, Ceftriaxone, Cefuroxime, Tetracycline, and Ciprofloxacin. In contrast, Augmentin, Gentamicin, and Meropenem demonstrated better effectiveness, with susceptibility rates of 41%, 47.7%, and 63.6%, respectively. Among *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates, 69.2% showed resistance to Ciprofloxacin, Ampicillin, Cefepime, Ceftazidime, Ceftriaxone, and Cefuroxime. For *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, 60% of isolates were susceptible to Piperacillin and Meropenem, while 70% were resistant to Ceftazidime. *Proteus* spp. showed susceptibility to Augmentin, Ceftazidime, Gentamicin, Meropenem, and Chloramphenicol. Meanwhile, *Acinetobacter baumannii* exhibited resistance to Cefepime, Ceftazidime, and Ciprofloxacin.[11]

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the prevalence and microbial profile of surgical infections, with a culture positivity rate of 12.8% and an SSI rate of 0.29%. Gram-negative bacteria, particularly *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *E. coli*, were the predominant isolates, followed closely by Gram-positive organisms like *Staphylococcus aureus*, with a significant proportion being methicillin-resistant (MRSA). High resistance rates were observed against commonly used antibiotics such as Penicillin, Amoxiclav, and Cefuroxime, underscoring the urgent need for antibiotic stewardship. The findings support the formulation of a localized antibiogram and reinforce the importance of infection control practices, including proper surgical techniques and timely, evidence-based antibiotic therapy.

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